

DISSIPATIV QATLAMLARNING ERKIN TEBRANISHLARI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada yarim tekislikda joylashgan qatlamlarning erkin tebranishlari o'rganiladi. Yarim tekis qatlamlardan iborat maxanik sistema reologik xossalari bir xil bo'lsa dissipativ bir jinsli, har xil bo'lsa dissipativ bir jinsli bolmagan sistema deb qaraladi. Masalada elastiklik nazariyasining yarim teskari usullari qo'llanilib, yechim tanlash yo'li bilan chegaraviy shartlardan foydalangan holda tebranish chastotalari aniqlanadi. Yechim tanlashdan hosil bo'ladigan bir jinsli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasining noldan farqli yechilarining mavjud bo'lish shartidan hosil bo'ladigan dispersiya tenglamasi Myuller usulida yechiladi, kompleks chastota qiymatlari aniqlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: elastik muhit, tekis qatlam, reologik xossasi, Lyame operatorlari, dispersiya tenglamasi, kompleks chastota, Lyame koeffitsiyentlari, Bessel funksiyalari, dispersiyatenglamasi.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются свободные колебания механическая система, состоящая из плоских слоистых тел, находящийся на полупространстве. Механическая система реологическая свойство, диссипативно однородная. В задаче применяется полу обратный метод теории упругости, выбираются решения удовлетворяющие дифференциальным уравнениям движения и граничные условия, составляются уравнения дисперсии. Из уравнения дисперсии определяются комплексные частоты колебаний методом Мюллера.

Ключевые слова: диссипативная среда, плоская система, уравнения дисперсии, комплексная частота, коэффициенты Ламе, скорости продольных и поперечных волн, функции Весселя, уравнения дисперсии.

Abstract. The article investigates the free vibrations of cylindrical bodies in flat media. In the problem, the semi-inverse method of the theory of elasticity is used, solutions are selected that satisfy the differential equations of motion and boundary conditions, dispersion equations are compiled. From the dispersion equation, the complex oscillation frequencies are determined by the Muller method.

Keywords: Elastic medium, piecewise homogeneous cylindrical system, dispersion equations, complex frequency, Lamé coefficients, velocities of longitudinal and transverse waves, Wessel functions, homogeneous algebraic system of equations.

Yer osti inshootlarining qurilishi yer(tuproq, muhit) mexanikasini o'rganishni taqozo etadi. Muhit va undagi inshoot mexanik sistema deb qaraladi. Ular har xil mexanik xossalarga ega bo'lganda bir jinsli bo'lmagan sistema hosil bo'ladi. Maqolada elastik muhit va dissipativ qatlamdan iborat bir jinsli bo'lmagan sistemalarning erkin tebranishlari o'rganiladi.

u_n, v_n, w_n – muhit va qatlamning x, y, z o'qlar bo'ylab ko'chishlari($n=1;2$). Tekis kuchlanganlik holatida $w_n=0$. u_n, v_n lar z ga bog'liq bo'lmaydi, deformatsiya bilan kuchlanish orasida bog'lanish Guk qonuni ko'rinishda olinadi. Dissipativlik xususiyatlari $\tilde{\lambda}_n, \tilde{\mu}_n$ – Lyame operator koeffitsientlari[3] bilan o'rganiladi:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \tilde{\lambda}_n &= \lambda_n \left[\varphi(t) - \int_0^t R_{\lambda_n}(t-\tau) \varphi(\tau) d\tau \right]; \\ \tilde{\mu}_n &= \mu_n \left[\varphi(t) - \int_0^t R_{\mu_n}(t-\tau) \varphi(\tau) d\tau \right]; \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

R_{λ_n}, R_{μ_n} – relaksatsiya yadrosi, t -vaqt, $\varphi(t)$ – ixtiyoriy funktsiya,

$$\lambda_n = \frac{E_n \nu_n}{(1 + \nu_n)(1 - 2\nu_n)}; \quad \mu_n = \frac{E_n}{2(1 + \nu_n)}; \quad \text{Lyame koeffitsientlari,}$$

ν_n – Puasson koeffitsiyenti;

$\sigma_{ij}, \varepsilon_{ij}$ – yarim fazo va qatlamning kuchlanish va deformatsiya tenzori komponentlari;

ρ_j – qatlam va muhit zichligi.

Kuchlanish ifodasini kuchlanishlarga nisbatan harakat tenglamalariga qo'yib, yarim fazo va qatlam uchun differensial tenglamalar sistemasi olinadi [1].

Differensial tenglamalar sistemasi bikr(жесткий) va sirpanuvchi(скользящий) kontaktlar uchun yechiladi. Birk kontaktda ham, shirpanuvchi kontaktda ham masalani noma'lumlar uchun yuqoridagi chegaraviy shartlarda yechish mumkin.

Masalaning yechimini elastiklik nazariyasining yarim teskari usulini qo'llab, yechimlar tanlash bilan yechiladi.

$$u_n = U_n \cdot \ell^{ik(x-ct)}; \quad (2)$$

$$g_n = V_n \cdot \ell^{ik(x-ct)};$$

U_n, V_n – amplitudani ifodalovchi vektor – funktsiya,

$k = k_R + ik_I$ - to'lqin soni,

$c = c_R + ic_I$ – kompleks fazaviy tezlik,

$\omega = kc$ – kompleks chastota,

η_n – o'zgarma son.

k_I, c_I – mavhum qismlar dissipativ jarayonlarning intensivligini xarakterlaydi.

Natijada xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalar sistemasi oddiy differensial tenglamalar sistemasiga keladi. A_n, B_n ga nisbatan hosil bo'lgan bir jinsli algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi noldan farqli yechimga ega bo'lish shartidan

$$[C_{ij}] = 0; \quad (3)$$

determinant tenglama ildizlari ikkinchi tartibli determinant ko'rinishidagi 4-tartibli tenglama bo'lib, to'rtta ildizi aniqlanadi.

(3)ning yechimlari Myuller usulida yechiladi. Myuller usulining qulayligi shundaki, chap tomondagi determinant yoyib o'tirilmaydi. Hosil bo'lgan transsendent tenglamaning uch nuqtadagi interpolatsion funksilari tuziladi. Funktsiyalarning shu nuqtalar atrofidagi nollari aniqlanadi.

Sistemaning dissipativlik xususiyatlari har xil, dissipativ bir jinsli bolmagan sistema, sistemaning reologik xossalari [2] bo'yicha olindi:

$$R_1 = R_2 = A \cdot \ell^{-\beta t / t^{1-\alpha}};$$

$$A = 0,01; \beta = 1; \alpha = 0,1; \theta = \rho_1 / \rho_2 = 0,75; \gamma = 0,01; \quad (4)$$

$\xi_j = kh$ – to'liq soni, $\gamma_j = \gamma_1 / h$. ξ_j - (0-8) intervalda variatsiyalandi.

Dissipativ bir jinsli bo'lmagan sistema o'rganildi. Yarim fazo elastik, $R_l = 0$. Qatlamning reologik xossalari (4) bo'yicha olindi. Bu holda kompleks chatota qiymatlari jips(jestkiy) kontaktda 1-grafik 6)da keltirilgan.

$$\delta = \min(-\omega_{Ik}); \quad k=1,2,3,\dots,N, \quad (5)$$

δ sistemaning dempferlash xossasini to'liq ifodalaydi. Dissipativ bir jinsli bo'lmagan sistema global dempferlash koeffisienti, ξ_j ning qiymatlariga bog'liq holda, birinchi, shuningdek, ikkinchi chastotaning mavhum qismlari bo'lishi ham mumkin. Bunday sohalarda δ global dempferlash koeffisienti aniq maksimumlarga erishadi(1-grafik).

1-grafik. Kompleks chastotaning to'liq soniga nisbatan o'zgarish grafigi(jips kontakt). Dissipativ bir jinsli bo'lmagan sistema.

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